

Title:

Recommendations of additional quality indicators for use in older adult residential long-term care: a RAND/UCLA Modified eDelphi Panel Method protocol

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Abstract

Background/Objectives

Long-term care facilities (LTCFs) in Switzerland have been obligated, since 2019, to report medical quality indicators to the Federal Office of Statistics. Data on six indicators in four clinical domains are collected: polypharmacy, pain (self-reported and assessor-rated), weight loss (malnutrition) and the use of physical restraints (bedrails or trunk fixation). While important, these depict only a partial view of a resident's quality of care and life. A multidimensional assessment of quality underpins this study's evaluation of additional quality domains and indicators for Swiss LTCFs.

Methods

A RAND/UCLA Modified eDelphi Panel Method will be conducted to reach a consensus among experts in long-term care (LTC) on additional quality indicators to recommend to the Swiss Federal Quality Commission. This incorporates several steps, beginning with a review of the literature, the results of which will be discussed during interviews with national experts on LTC. These findings will inform a two-round eDelphi survey. Workshops with LTCF residents and family members are also planned, the findings of which will provide a user perspective to eDelphi panel participants during a virtual panel discussion between the first and second survey rounds. eDelphi panel members will be asked to rate quality indicators according to their importance (relevance and value), feasibility (practical and measurable in Swiss older adult care homes), and actionability within the LTCF. RAND criteria will be applied to establish consensus.

Discussion

The findings will inform the recommendation of further medical quality indicators for Swiss LTCFs. The collective expertise and perspectives on the quality indicators will be relevant in other settings where there is interest in implementing quality indicators that offer insight into quality of care and quality of life of LTC residents.

Keywords

Long-term care, older adults, quality, quality indicators, eDelphi method

Introduction

In Switzerland, as in other countries, continuous care quality development is an important goal in residential long-term care (LTC) for older people (Smith et al., 2024). Medical quality indicators (MQIs) are one element of quality development, providing information to a range of stakeholders and serving at least three purposes. First, at the facility level, MQIs are used by long term care facility (LTCF) personnel to identify areas for development. Thus, MQIs need to be perceived as important, data collection for the MQIs must be feasible, and the underlying issues they assess must fall within their realm of control (action-able by LTCF staff). Second, MQIs are used for monitoring purposes at a policy level, such as by the cantons. Thirdly, as the MQI data are publicly reported, they must provide interpretable data about aspects of care provided in a LTCF that interested parties can access.

LTC systems are currently faced with limited and changing resources, as well as increasingly diversified and complex case mixes (Barker et al., 2021; Karzig-Roduner et al., 2021; Van Den Brink et al., 2013). Hence, quality indicators that are viewed as important, feasible, , and actionable, for stakeholders at all levels (e.g., cantonal and federal authorities, facility staff and residents/family members) are essential for planning and implementing care quality development, as well as for public reporting and benchmarking at regional and national levels (Schang et al., 2021). As a result of a modification to the Federal Insurance Law in 1996 (LAMal, Art. 59a), long-term care facilities in Switzerland have been obligated, since 2019, to report medical quality indicators (LAMal Art 22a) to the Federal Office of Statistics. Following an extensive consultation process, the first indicator set was proposed in 2015 and includes six indicators on four clinical domains: polypharmacy, pain (self-reported and assessor-rated), weight loss (malnutrition) and the use of physical restraints (bedrails or seating that does not allow rising/trunk fixation) (Zúñiga et al., 2019). The current indicators focus on clinical aspects, providing only a partial perspective of the quality of the care received by residents. They do not include, for example, indicators of person-centred care, psychosocial aspects of care in a LTCF, personal preferences or quality of life perceptions (Kalideen et al., 2022). Moreover, the social aspects that help make a LTC facility feel like home are often missed or not taken into consideration (Leichsenring, 2019). By focusing on clinical aspects that emphasise problems in care, the potential positive elements and outcomes of care, such as the maintenance of mental and physical capacity are not considered. Quality of care and quality of life domains that extend beyond clinical care are seldom considered in LTCFs due to their subjectivity and intricacies (Atkinson et al., 2010; Joling et al., 2018), despite high quality care in LTC moving in parallel to high quality of life, both goals of residential long-term care.

Quality of life and quality of care are interconnected but distinct concepts (Hoffmann et al., 2010). Quality of life is a concept lacking a consensus definition which includes both objective assessments and subjective perceptions of health, functional ability, psychological, social and economic wellbeing (Rodríguez-Fuertes et al., 2023; Saha et al., 2023). As a multidimensional concept, it is used to frame indicators of quality in long-term care based on personal preferences of care recipients, and includes citizenship values like freedom, justice, and autonomy, as well as experiences of dignity, privacy, and safety (Hoffmann et al., 2010). Quality of care is similarly difficult to define, and its definition is continuously evolving with differences across healthcare settings. For example, the World Health Organisation defines care quality as care that is effective, safe, and person-centred, while other definitions place greater emphasis on desired health outcomes and overall efficiency (Busse et al., 2019). However, the fact that LTC settings provide a combination of acute, post-acute, chronic, and social care render the identification of specific health outcomes problematic and complex (OECD/European Commission, 2013). Amplifying the challenges are the differing levels of care between residents, multimorbidity, the frequent presentation of cognitive impairment and the progressive degeneration that is expected in LTC settings for older people.

The literature on quality indicators usefully distinguishes between indicator types, including structural indicators that assess features of the context of care (e.g., staff levels, the physical environment), processes of care (e.g., person-centred care) or outcomes themselves (e.g., levels of reported pain) (Donabedian, 1988). In addition to the importance of considering all three types, recent scholarship also underscores the importance of constructing indicator sets that cover all necessary or desired domains (Marang-Van De Mheen & Vincent, 2023). This approach aims to avoid selecting multiple indicators on a single domain and few or none on others, which could result in an un-balanced or partial assessment (e.g., assessment of clinical outcomes and care processes, but not the resident's perspective). Indeed, the extant literature highlights how long-term care quality incorporates both clinical quality and user experience as the main dimensions of quality (OECD/European Commission, 2013). In 2010, an EU funded project, *Quality Management by Result-oriented Indicators - Towards Benchmarking in Residential Care for Older People*, produced a handbook entitled *Measuring Progress: indicators for care homes*, revealing result-oriented quality indicators used for care homes based on five European countries' shared experiences (Hoffmann et al., 2010). Among the key domains identified were the quality of (nursing) care, with a special focus on quality-of-life, in part given the recognised challenge of making a declaration about an individual's quality of life based on objective data from indicators.

In Switzerland, the reporting of medical quality indicators has been established, but is still in its infancy. Given the limitations of the specific focus of the existing national MQI set, and the potential for a multi-dimensional assessment to provide additional information beyond medical outcomes, we outline three inter-related reviews of the international literature that will permit us to identify the central domains related to quality of care and quality of life, and the indicators, including those which are resident-reported, that can facilitate their assessment in residential LTC for older people. These will feed into the consensus process that will be used to identify and recommend further MQIs.

The aim of this study is to explore, and build a consensus for, additional MQIs for Swiss LTCFs, with the final aim of formulating concrete and applicable recommendations to the Federal Quality Commission. To achieve this, a RAND/UCLA Modified eDelphi Panel Method will be conducted to reach a consensus across experts in the field (Fitch et al., 2001).

Methods

Study design

The study described in this protocol is one part of a broader programme entitled: National Implementation Programme: Strengthening quality of care in partnership with residential long-term care facilities for older people (NIP-Q-UPGRADE). The programme is financed by the Swiss Federal Quality Commission (FQC), led by ARTISET, via the trade association CURAVIVA, and senesuisse, two sector-specific associations in Switzerland, and is carried out in collaboration with the Institute for Nursing Science at the University of Basel, La Source School of Nursing, University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland and the Competence Centre on Ageing at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI).

The RAND/UCLA Modified eDelphi Panel Method will be used. Although commonly applied to developing clinical practice guidelines, in this study, it is adapted to build consensus on further indicators of quality consistent with previous work (Boulkedid et al., 2011, 2013; Derendorf et al., 2023; Filiatreault et al., 2023; Fitch et al., 2001; Ohtera et al., 2017). It brings together evidence and expert opinion through asking panellists to individually rate items, discuss identified disagreements, and then re-rate the set of items. It is a multi-step process that begins with a literature review that informs an initial draft of eDelphi survey items, the selection of a panel of experts and rating criteria, a first round of rating via an online survey, a (virtual) meeting to discuss disagreements, and a second, final round of rating. These steps form the basis of a summary of consensus areas. In this study,

additional steps will be integrated: expert interviews exploring the findings of the literature review to support the development of the eDelphi survey items, and resident/family workshops exploring the topic of further quality indicators to elicit the user-perspective. The findings of the latter will be presented to the eDelphi panel members at the virtual meeting and incorporated into the second and final eDelphi rating round. A summary of the proposed method is presented in Figure 1 and each step is described in the following sections.

Figure 1. Adapted RAND/UCLA Modified eDelphi Panel Method process.

Literature review

The first step of the study described in this protocol is a literature review that was subdivided into three rapid systematic reviews. The first rapid review (RR1) reviewed the literature on frameworks of quality of life and quality of care in the context of residential long-term care for older people internationally. The second rapid review reviewed quality indicators used internationally in the assessment of quality in the same context. The third rapid review reviewed patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) and patient-reported experience measures (PREMs) used internationally as quality indicators in LTC. The rapid review method was selected as a simplified systematic process to provide an overview of evidence

in a short time frame to serve as support in informing health policy and services (Khangura et al., 2012; Tricco et al., 2015) By restricting the search strategy and the scope of a study with a focused question, a rapid literature review is a simplified yet rigorous method that uses components of the systematic approach to summarize evidence (Smela et al., 2023). The rapid review methodology outlined by Smela et al. (2023) was followed and as indicated, the PRISMA checklist was used to guide the three rapid reviews represented in the PRISMA flow chart (Appendix 1) (Page et al., 2021).

Four databases were consulted for each rapid review: CINAHL Complete and SocINDEX with Full Text via EBSCO, PubMed, and PsycINFO. Inclusion criteria applied systematically to the three rapid reviews were sources published between 2013 and 2024, and no language filters were applied. For all three rapid reviews, Braun and Clark’s thematic analysis process was followed: the initial themes were reassessed, consolidated, regrouped, and renamed (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The screening of titles was completed by two researchers, with random agreement check of a small sample (5%) by a third researcher. Abstract screening was performed in the same way; and full text screening and data extraction was completed by two researchers for each rapid review. A third researcher random checked the full text screenings in the three reviews for agreement. The consolidated results outline two main concepts: quality of care and quality of life, and the relative domains that emerged (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Quality domains.

National expert interviews

Eight to ten semi-structured qualitative interviews are planned with national experts on the topic of quality in residential long-term care for older people. Based on the consolidated findings of the literature reviews, the aims are to explore views on quality domains and themes, and to compile recommendations for quality indicators that will subsequently feed into the RAND/UCLA Modified eDelphi panel method. Potential interviewees include representatives from national associations related to ageing, health, quality of life and quality of care in LTC. Experts from social gerontology, integrated care, and clinical ethics will also be included. The selection of experts will be purposeful to elicit multidisciplinary perspectives of quality. The experts will be recruited via email. If they are unable to participate, we will welcome their suggestions on other suitable participants from their organization or network.

The quality domains and themes identified in the literature reviews will feed into the semi-structured interview guide that will include open-ended questions on the concepts of quality of care and life and their relevant domains, and a Likert scale (0-10) assessing the importance of quality domains. Data from these interviews will be analyzed using NVivo software following Braun and Clark's thematic analysis process (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Findings will contribute to the development of the eDelphi survey, described in the next section.

RAND/UCLA Modified eDelphi Panel Method

Selection, size and recruitment of expert panel

A heterogeneous sample of experts in the areas of LTC for older adults and quality of care and quality of life in ageing will be recruited to participate in the eDelphi Panel. At this stage, in addition to national experts, we also involve international experts to leverage the expertise of countries where quality development strategies are more mature, and to include best practices and knowledge from other contexts (Boulkedid et al., 2011; Fink et al., 1984). Avoiding disciplinary or individual dominance is a strength of the eDelphi technique that allows for multisectoral, global expertise of participants to be consolidated (Hasson et al., 2000). The expertise of those working in the field is also recognised and we include nurses, nurse experts, quality managers and LTC directors as well, preferably representing the 3 main linguistic regions of Switzerland (Swiss-German, Swiss-French and Swiss-Italian). Inclusion criteria to participate in the study include the ability to complete the eDelphi in English, willingness to participate, direct field experience and/or research experience in the aforementioned fields, and nomination via snowball sampling method by a contacted expert. The ideal panel size for an eDelphi study is not defined in the literature, though larger panels

increase reliability of group agreement, and panels with fewer than six participants risk not providing reliable estimates of consensus (Filiatreault et al., 2023). The target minimum sample size (N=24) allows for a maximum dropout rate of 50% assuring the minimum participation rate for the final round. Experts will be recruited via email, using a multipronged approach including the networks of the co-authors and snowballing sampling, and via postings on websites and newsletters of relevant sector associations. Prior to providing informed consent to participate (online), participants will be asked to read the information sheet describing the study, including the background and aims of the study, and the reasons why their commitment to participate in both rounds and the virtual panel discussion, is ideal. We will also briefly describe the context of the MQIs for residential LTC in Switzerland for those who might be unfamiliar with the legal framework or existing MQIs. Consent will be collected upon initiating the first round and will be asked for the entire eDelphi process. Participants have the possibility to withdraw at any time during data collection. Recruitment will be monitored at first contact to create a multisectoral and multidisciplinary sample, but snowballing will make it challenging to prevent over and/or under representation of one expert group or discipline. The recruitment process will be planned over 3 weeks, with a reminder sent each week. If an expert does not respond after the 3 weeks, the expert will not be contacted again. The timeline will be extended by 2 weeks if the minimum target sample size is not met within the first period of recruitment. The same process will be applied to the second round. It is important to acknowledge participation fatigue and attrition rates, thus a round will be accepted as valid if there is a 50% response rate. For each round, the survey will remain active for four weeks, with a weekly email reminder, and/or a thank you email after completion.

Survey design and development

This modified eDelphi study will give participants pre-existing information in the form of closed ended items for ranking domains and indicators with the opportunity to provide comments for each item and justify ratings (Hasson et al., 2000). The Qualtrics software will be used to develop the survey. Participants will be asked to rate quality indicators according to their **importance** (relevance and value to quality of Swiss LTCFs), **feasibility** (practical and measurable in Swiss LTCFs), and **actionability** (potential for LTCF staff to effectuate change leading to concrete development goals). Each item will be rated on a 9-point Likert scale (1-9), where tertiles will delineate low scores (1-3 not at all important, feasible, or actionable), average scores (4-6 somewhat important, feasible, or actionable), and high scores (7-9 very important, feasible, or actionable). A statement of the rationale/evidence from the literature review and expert interview findings for each domain will be presented to inform participants' ratings.

Procedures

Two rounds will be conducted, with a virtual panel discussion between them.

The objective of round one is to obtain participant demographic data to describe the sample, to collect data on initial judgements on the quality indicators, and potential ideas for alternative domains and/or indicators. Prior to the second round, a virtual panel discussion will be held to allow an exchange of reasons for disagreements, offering participants the opportunity to reflect on their ratings considering the viewpoint of other experts in the group prior to completing the second round. Resident and family workshops will also be held between the rounds to explore the user-perspective of the quality indicators resulting from the first eDelphi round. An overview of the results from the first round and the LTC resident/family/staff workshop findings will be presented at the eDelphi virtual panel discussion. Both quantitative (median, minimal, and maximal ratings) and qualitative (abstract of panel comments) feedback will be provided to the panel, along with the participant's own responses indicating their position relative to the group.

In round two of the eDelphi, the results of the virtual panel discussion will be presented including: (a) items rated with disagreement; (b) items rated as uncertain (median within the second tertile 4-6); (c) re-worded or new items based on virtual panel discussion input. Items with no disagreement with median ratings of 6 or below (in the first and second tertiles) will be discarded thus not presented in the second round.

Defining consensus

There is no definition for reaching consensus in Delphi studies, but defining the criteria for consensus is considered important (Boulkedid et al., 2011; Diamond et al., 2014; Filiatreault et al., 2023). Following the results of the second round, each domain and indicator will be classified as 'important, uncertain or unimportant'; 'feasible, uncertain, infeasible'; and 'actionable, uncertain, inactionable' in accordance with median scores and levels of disagreement. For example, regarding the importance of the indicator, items with median scores in the first tertile (1-3) are considered 'unimportant', those with scores in the second tertile (4-6) are considered 'uncertain', and those in the third tertile (7-9) are considered 'important'. The same process is applied to feasibility and actionability scores. Any items where there is disagreement (less than 80% rating scores in same tertile), not considering the median scores, are classified as lacking consensus. Using the RAND criteria to establish consensus, it is defined as 80% of rating scores within the 3-point tertile of the overall median (Fitch et al., 2001).

Stopping and item removal

Criteria for stopping the eDelphi process include high dropout rate or low attrition to panel workshop or the second round. Removal criteria for quality indicators from the eDelphi process after both rounds is 80% of ratings in the lowest tertile (1-3), and overall panel median in the same tertile (1-3) for at least one of the three criteria (importance, feasibility, actionability).

Round one

In the first round, we will ask participants for limited demographic information to describe the sample, followed by the first rating of importance, feasibility, and actionability on the quality indicators emerging from the literature reviews. Participants will be able to leave comments after each indicator, as well as suggest alternative quality indicators. Quality indicators with scores in the first tertile (i.e., unimportant, unfeasible, or inactionable (1-3)) will be removed (80% of ratings in the lowest tertile (1-3), and overall panel median in the same tertile). Items producing disagreement will be discussed in the virtual panel discussion, as will any alternatives suggested by participants.

Resident workshop

Four LTCF workshops will be held, each representing one of the four Swiss Regional Health Director's conferences, to include the lived experience of LTC residents and family members. Participants will be provided an information sheet describing the study and the objectives of the workshop, as well as a consent form to sign. During the workshop, participants will be asked to discuss their experiences and priorities with respect to quality indicators included in the first eDelphi round. Data will be collected through note taking and will be analysed thematically using Nvivo software. Findings will be presented in the eDelphi virtual panel discussion to offer participants the user perspective in their evaluations.

Virtual panel discussion

During the virtual panel discussion, the moderator guides participants to share their reasoning on indicators for which there was disagreement. Confronting differences of opinions may lead participants to more 'consistent and logical positions' (Broder et al., 2022 p. XX).. Discussions can include definitions and clarifications allowing participants to reach a common understanding of the items they are rating, potentially reducing disagreement. Prior to and in preparation for the virtual panel discussion, an overview of the first round results and the resident and family workshop(s) findings will be sent to each panelist. Results of the virtual panel discussion are used to develop the questionnaire for the second and final eDelphi round.

Round two

In the second round, the aim is to reach consensus on indicators. Each participant re-rates the items, with a new consideration of the user perspective, and what other participants rated and why. A personalized questionnaire is sent with the results of the virtual panel discussion including: (a) items rated with disagreement; (b) items rated as uncertain (median within the second tertile 4-6); (c) re-worded or new items based on panel discussion input. Items with overall panel median of 7–9, with 80% of ratings within the 3-point tertile of the overall median, will be considered as having reached consensus. Any items where there is disagreement, not considering the median scores, are classified as lacking consensus.

Data analysis

Data will be downloaded from the Qualtrics software following each round and analysed in STATA in order to provide feedback to participants, and to exclude quality indicators from the virtual panel discussion and the second round. The final results from the second round will be analysed with the objective of identifying indicators for assessing quality in Swiss LTCFs using the concepts of importance, feasibility, and actionability.

Ethics and dissemination

A Clarification of Responsibility was submitted to the Cantonal Ethical Committee and they have decided that that full ethical review is not required for this study. All data will be collected online using the Qualtrics software, which is a secure platform that abides by Swiss privacy and data protection regulations. Informed consent will be obtained by all participants.

Dissemination of the findings will be done through traditional methods such as reports, scientific peer-reviewed publications, and conferences, as well as webinars held in each Swiss language region for field professionals. A final report will be submitted to the sector associations of the NIP-Q-UPGRADE programme who will submit the findings to the Swiss Federal Quality Commission. Inclusion of various stakeholders and multidisciplinary experts assure transferability of this study's results to care homes in three Swiss language regions. This study will identify further indicators evaluated as important, feasible and actionable by national and international experts and based on scientific evidence, to be considered in LTCFs to assess quality and facilitate continuous quality development.

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APPENDIX 1
PRISMA flow chart

